

A treatise on the rulings of the people of Dhimma (رسالة في أحكام اهل الذمة)

By Bilyaminu Muhammad, Umaru Musa 'Yar-Adua University Katsina, Nigeria

Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Islamic Jurisprudence, Shari'a, Islamic Traditions

Imam Abdu al-Karim al-Maghili wrote a brief book titled A Treatise on the Rulings of the People of Dhimma on his visit to the ancient Kano locality in modern-day northern Nigeria. While there, he observed the settlement of non-Muslims who were expected to abide by specific rules to live peacefully and enjoy certain privileges within the Islamic empire. The book was divided into three chapters: the first dealt with warnings to Muslims to stay away from non-believers; the second dealt with paying homage to the Islamic State; and the third dealt with the predicament of the Jews of the time. Every chapter begins with Qur'anic verses, which are pertinent to the rules and subject of the chapter, followed by the Prophet Muhammad's (SAW) sayings on the topic. In addition, the opinions of eminent Islamic scholars are offered to clarify the meaning of the traditions and verses cited that are typically backed by pertinent stanzas and other sources to substantiate Dhimmi's decisions.

Date Range: 1425 BCE - 1505 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: محمد بن عبد الكريم بن محمد المغيلي التلمساني (1503). رسالة في أحكام اهل الذمة. الأزهر الشريف مصر

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.alazharonline.org>

– Source 1 Description: محمد بن عبد الكريم بن محمد المغيلي التلمساني (1503). رسالة في أحكام اهل الذمة. الأزهر الشريف مصر

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://shamela.ws/book/21747>

– Source 1 Description: محمد بن أبي بكر بن أيوب بن سعد شمس الدين ابن قيم الجوزية. (1997). أحكام أهل الذمة. رمادى للنشر - الدمام

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: Light brown paper.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple
– No

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– Yes

Notes: Some copies of the book are kept in mosques for the benefit of Muslims.

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument
– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point
– No

↳ Cave(s)
– No

- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - Yes
- ↳ Library/archive
 - Yes
- ↳ Specify
 - Specify: Bookshopes and market places.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The document was written up and then published by the old Kano emirate.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The author was rewarded for the publishing of the text.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: The emirate of the ancient Kano state supported the production of the text financially.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

Notes: Even though the government employs some religious specialists to help the emirate with its spiritual concerns, political authorities are distinct from religious leaders.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Some officials assisted in reproducing the text in the region.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– No

Notes: Political officials and religious officials remained different institutions that has different responsibilities, even though both support each other.

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

Notes: The polity collect tribute from Dhimmis on the prescription of the text.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– Yes

Notes: Some legal codes of the polity in respect to Dhimmis were drive from the text.

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

Notes: The polity supported the production of the text by other means.

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

Notes: Some are engaged on part time base.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Religious specialists are predominantly men, yet some educated women wield power over the feminine gender.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Yes

Notes: Most of the people in the region belong to Hausa-Fulani ethnic group.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Notes: Religious specialists engaged in other activities in addition to the reproduction of the text.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

Notes: Some religious officials are identified as Imams, judges, teachers, etc.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Some classes of specialists are trained in separate places, such as judges.

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Religious officials are cared for by the polity.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: Only the Qur'an is considered religious scripture to the Muslims.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The text was only written in Arabic language.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 18000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 20000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 18000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Birthrate, Beathrate and Migration.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 18000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 18000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Birthrate, Deathrate and Migration.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

- Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)
- Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

- No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

- Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

- No

Notes: The text restricted discussion on the principles of relating to the non-believers in Muslim society.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

- Yes

Notes: The text recommended proselytizing to have the conversion of the people to the religion of Allah.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

- Yes

Notes: The primary goal of the ethical standards discussed in the text is to persuade unbelievers to adopt Islam as their religion.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

- Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

- Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

- Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

- Yes

Notes: The promised reward of proselytizing in the text will be gotten in hereafter.

- ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
- ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes
- ↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes
- ↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– No
Notes: The principle upon which the text was written did not allow coercing in converting others to the religion of Islam.
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– Yes
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
– No
Notes: Proselytizing is not restricted to a specific period.
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
– No
Notes: Proselytizing is not limited to a particular place.
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
– No
Notes: Proselytizing is generally directed to the entire non-Muslims.
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
– No
- ↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Moral ethics.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: According to the text, institutionalized police are responsible for upholding the law and enforcing commands in the Islamic state about non-Muslims.

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

↳ Execution?

– Yes

Notes: The text orders the execution of a Muslim to have reverted to another religion.

↳ Exile?

– No

↳ Corporal punishments?

– No

↳ Ostracism?

– Yes

↳ Seizure of property?

– No

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: But the text works on the Islamic lunar calendar.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: The material body and spirit work together for the existence and life of the human being.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: The body and mind are considered different for the qualities associated with each entity.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or

spirit?

– Yes

Notes: The death of a human being terminates the corporeal body while the soul leaves for an undisclosed location.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Notes: The actual belief of the majority goes to the dualism of the corporeal body and spirit body, while the minority view goes to the unity of the two.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The location of the afterlife remains hidden from all except the creator of all.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: Belief in the afterlife is ascertained and accepted by the group.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: Arabic is believed to be the language of the afterlife.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is rejected in the religion of the text.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: No goods are accepted in burial.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: The deceased body is being washed and shrouded.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: The text accepts funeral prayers for the dead body.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: The nature of the Supreme High God is not known to any.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Notes: The power of the Supreme High God controls the underworld.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Notes: The elites remain among the servants of the Supreme High God.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Supreme High God create the world.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the Supreme High God has no restriction in the affairs of human beings.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
 - Notes: Humans cannot fathom the Supreme High God's emotions.
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: Destiny is in the hands of the Supreme High God.
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supreme High God communicates to some selected messengers.
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: The communication is restricted to messengers and prophets alone.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit of man is present right before the coming to the world.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

Notes: The human spirit is not visible to the eyes.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

Notes: The human spirit is unaware of the earth before it descends into the world.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Yes
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not have the power to know what is in the mind.
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - No
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
 - ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Angels extend revelation to the messengers on the directives of their lord.

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Jinns interact with their fellow evildoers.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: Emotions of supernatural beings are not visible to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: Jinns are described as having a desire for food, unlike Angels.

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: Movement from one place to another.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
 - Yes

- ↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest
 - Yes
 - ↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
 - Yes
 - ↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
 - No
 - ↳ Other sexual practices
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– Specify: Animals

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings mete out punishment for the wrongdoings of a person.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: The High god gives directives of the punishment to Angels against the evildoers.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Many Angels in Hellfire administer the punishment.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

Notes: The punishment is severe.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Other form of punishment

– Specify: Extreme burning in the Hellfire.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: Some punishments are meted out in the life situation.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: Total failure in life.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Angels record rewards on a good deeds of Muslims.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: Only the High God bestows the reward.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Angels monitor the deeds of Muslims to record rewards in their books.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

Notes: Rewards are awarded systematically.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: Some achievements in life result from the rewards of good deeds.

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

–Specify: Successful life.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention messianic beliefs as it restricted discussion on the principles of relating to the unbelievers within the community of Muslims.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: Eschaton will be at the end of the life.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: The time of the eschaton is unspecified.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

Notes: The time is not known.

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The time is unspecified.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
– No

↳ Divine judgment event
– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world
– No
Notes: The world ends by the period of the eschaton.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
– No
Notes: Eschaton marked the time of eternal life.

↳ Establishment of new political system
– No
Notes: The life is under the control of the High God.

↳ Establishment of new religious system
– No
Notes: Religion terminates by the end of the world.

↳ Other form of eschatology?
– Specify: Paradise, Hellfire, etc.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
– No
Notes: All will be finished by the end of the eschaton.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?
– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?
– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: Celibacy is directed at those who do not have a legal spouse or partner.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires Muslims to fast in the month of Ramadan.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: Obligatory and voluntary charity is expected on the personal properties.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires regular attendance of congregational prayers.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires risk-taking in the stance of protecting the religion of Islam.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends voluntary ritual practices.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 10

Notes: The intervals depend on personal choice.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 100

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 3

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– Yes

↳ Food taboos?

– No

↳ Hair?

– Yes

↳ Dress?

– No

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Congregational prayers

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention sacrifice for the adoration of a sacred place.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No element of destruction is associated with the text.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the syllabus taught by the formal education of the region.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified Islamic schools as formal educational institutions.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated the bureaucracy concerning the non-Muslims within the community of the Islamic state.

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

Notes: The text regulated bureaucracy regulation permanently.

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– No

Notes: The text regulated tribute collection as part of the revenue to the Islamic state.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: Social interaction.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned tribute collection on those non-Muslims within the empire of Islam for the

privileges they received from the state.

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text called for warfare when the unbelievers stand against or hinder the development of the religion of Allah.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Notes: The text mentioned military force as a mechanism of depending on the religion of Allah.

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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